

BRIEF REPORT

Evaluation of Mediterranean sponges as natural samplers for environmental DNA (eDNA)

[version 1; peer review: 2 not approved]

Nicolas Garcia-Seyda ⁴

¹Aix Marseille Univ, Université de Toulon, CNRS, IRD, MIO, Marseille, 13288, France²Tropical Marine Ecology of Pacific and Indian Oceans - UMR 9220, Research Institute for Development (RID), Noumea, 98848, New Caledonia³NGS consultancy, Marseille, 13008, France⁴Argaly, Sainte-Hélène-du Lac, 73800, France

V1 **First published:** 17 Mar 2025, **5:69**
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19755.1>
Second version: 06 Oct 2025, **5:69**
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19755.2>
Latest published: 10 Mar 2026, **5:69**
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19755.3>

Abstract

Marine sponges have emerged as effective natural samplers of environmental DNA (eDNA), offering a promising alternative for biodiversity monitoring. By filtering large volumes of seawater, sponges accumulate eDNA from surrounding communities, potentially enhancing species detection in marine environments where conventional water sampling is limited. In this study, we evaluated the eDNA recovery efficiency of seven Mediterranean sponge species to identify optimal candidates for biomonitoring. *Axinella verrucosa* outperformed other tested species, highlighting its potential for long-term biodiversity assessments. Our results align with previous findings that low microbial abundance (LMA) sponges recover more eDNA than high microbial abundance (HMA) species, reinforcing the need for targeted sponge selection in future studies. Detected fish taxa were all bottom dwelling, supporting the relevance of sponge eDNA for monitoring cryptic species and benthic habitats. As eDNA-based monitoring advances, sponge sampling offers a valuable complement to water eDNA surveys, particularly in habitats where conventional sampling is challenging.

Plain Language Summary

Marine sponges naturally filter seawater and collect tiny traces of DNA (eDNA) from nearby organisms. This makes them useful for detecting marine species, especially in places where traditional water sampling is difficult. In this study, we tested seven Mediterranean species to see

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3	4	5
version 3 (revision) 10 Mar 2026					 view
version 2 (revision) 06 Oct 2025	 view				
version 1 17 Mar 2025	 view				

1. **Dannise V. Ruiz-Ramos** , University of Maryland Eastern Shore, Princess Anne, USA
2. **Ramon Gallego** , Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain
3. **Mykle Hoban**
4. **Rosie Dowell**
5. **Rachael Ununuma Chidugu-Ogborigbo**

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

which ones were best at capturing eDNA. *Axinella verrucosa* performed the best, meaning it could be an option for long-term biodiversity monitoring. Our results also confirmed that sponges with fewer internal microbes (LMA sponges) collect more eDNA than those with high microbial loads (HMA sponges). Most of the fish detected were bottom-dwelling species, showing that sponge eDNA is particularly useful for studying life at the sea bottom.

Keywords

Environmental DNA (eDNA), natural sampler DNA (nsDNA), Fish Metabarcoding, Marine sponges, Benthic biodiversity, *Axinella verrucosa*, Sponge-based biomonitoring

H2020

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions \(MSCA\)](#) gateway.

Corresponding author: Nicolas Garcia-Seyda (nicolas.garcia_seyda@ird.fr)

Author roles: **Garcia-Seyda N:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Garcia M:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Guillemain D:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Bonin A:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No [713750]. Also the European FEDER Fund under project 1166-39417, and the Labex Corail fund.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Garcia-Seyda N *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Garcia-Seyda N, Garcia M, Guillemain D and Bonin A. **Evaluation of Mediterranean sponges as natural samplers for environmental DNA (eDNA) [version 1; peer review: 2 not approved]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:69 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19755.1>

First published: 17 Mar 2025, 5:69 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19755.1>

Introduction

Environmental DNA (eDNA) has emerged as a revolutionary tool for marine biodiversity monitoring, offering a valuable complement to traditional methods based on visual surveys or species capture¹. eDNA-based approaches often demonstrate superior sensitivity, particularly for detecting species that are rare, cryptic, small, nocturnal, or otherwise elusive, which are frequently missed by conventional techniques². A significant bottleneck in current methodologies is the time-consuming water filtration process, typically restricted to surface waters due to the logistical challenges of sampling at depth. This limitation may result in the loss of valuable information on benthic biodiversity. While technological advances, such as submersible pumps and robotic sampling devices^{3,4}, are being developed to enable deeper sampling, they often remain prohibitively expensive. Additionally, for divers using manual underwater pumps, filtration time is constrained by bottom time and decompression limits.

A promising, low-tech alternative has been proposed by using marine sponges as natural eDNA samplers⁵. These benthic organisms filter large volumes of water daily, possess a rapid regeneration capacity, and have been successfully applied for biodiversity assessments in diverse ecosystems, including the North Atlantic⁶, Arctic⁷, Southern Ocean^{8,9}, and the Indo-Pacific¹⁰. These studies have shown that different sponge species exhibit varying eDNA yields, which have been attributed to differences in metabolism, pumping rates, and associated microbial communities. For instance, sponges are categorized into low microbial abundance (LMA) and high microbial abundance (HMA)¹¹, a factor influencing eDNA recovery with LMA species showing superior recovery rates^{7,12}. Identifying the species that maximize eDNA recovery under standardized conditions is thus essential before implementing large-scale monitoring campaigns. Such comparisons, to our knowledge, have only been conducted in controlled aquaria experiments¹², as eDNA recovery in natural settings is subject to additional confounding factors due to actual differences in fish occupancy and environmental parameters at the time of sampling.

In the Mediterranean Sea, despite the seminal study using opportunistic samples from two local sponge species⁵, systematic assessments of their eDNA sampling capacity are missing. The Northwestern Mediterranean façade is particularly rich in sponges, with steep walls and coralligenous habitats providing optimal conditions for sponge growth¹³. This region also hosts several marine protected areas (MPAs)¹⁴, where ongoing biomonitoring efforts could greatly benefit from novel eDNA-based approaches for biodiversity assessment. Here, we evaluated seven cosmopolitan Mediterranean sponge species thriving at a single site (coralligenous wall) to compare their effectiveness for eDNA recovery. By sampling 19 specimens under uniform environmental conditions and using a standardized processing protocol, we identified marked differences in eDNA recovery across species. Our results highlight *Axinella verrucosa* as the most promising candidate for future eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring efforts. Conversely, our findings also suggest certain species may be less effective as natural samplers, underscoring the importance of species selection in sponge-based eDNA studies.

Methods

Field work

Sampling was conducted on May 14, 2024, at the southern tip of Frioul Island, Marseille (Cap Caveau; 43° 15.614'N / 5° 17.360'E) between 10 and 11 a.m. Three specimens were sampled for each sponge species, except for *Aplysina cavemicola* and *Axinella verrucosa*, for which only two individuals were found at the site. Biopsies were excised using a blunt-ended diving knife at a depth of 10 meters, in an area characterized by a rocky vertical wall colonized by benthic organisms, descending to a sandy plain at 14 meters (Figure 1). Water temperature at the time of sampling was 17°C. Samples of the same species were stored in Ziploc bags within a diving mesh-bag and were transferred upon surfacing to a cooler with seawater for transport. Within 1–1.5 hours, excess water was removed, and biopsies were dried on paper tissue before being transferred into 50 mL falcon tubes with absolute ethanol. Samples were stored at -20°C until further processing.

Sample processing

Sponge tissues (0.5 cm³) were blotted dry with paper tissue, as outlined in Harper *et al.* (2023)¹⁵, before being chopped with a sterile scalpel on a petri dish. DNA extraction followed a modified Qiagen Blood & Tissue Kit protocol¹⁶. Briefly, sponge fragments were placed in 2 mL Eppendorf tubes and mixed with 720 µL Buffer ATL and 80 µL Proteinase K before incubation at 56°C overnight. An extraction control without starting material was included to detect potential contaminations. The next day, lysates (600 µL) were transferred to new tubes, combined sequentially with 600 µL Buffer AL and 600 µL 100% ethanol, and loaded onto DNeasy Mini spin columns in 2 mL collection tubes. After centrifugation at 6,000 × g for 1 min, the flowthroughs were discarded, and the process was repeated until all lysates had passed through the columns. The membranes were washed with 500 µL Buffer AW1 and centrifuged at 6,000 × g for 1 min, followed by a second wash with 500 µL Buffer AW2 and centrifugation at 20,000 × g for 3 min. Residual wash buffer was removed by an additional centrifugation at 20,000 × g for 1 min. DNA was eluted by adding 200 µL of preheated (56°C) AE buffer to the membranes, incubating for 1 min at room temperature, and

Figure 1. Sampling site. Underwater photography of the coralligenous wall where sponge specimens were sampled.

centrifuging at $6,000 \times g$ for 1 min. Following DNA extraction, qPCR was conducted using Fish16S primers¹⁷ to assess fish eDNA presence and optimize amplification conditions. This primer set was chosen because it was recently shown to recover a greater diversity of fish species than other primer pairs in a Mediterranean site¹⁸. The qPCR mix consisted of 10 μL of SsoAdvanced™ Universal SYBR® Green Supermix (BioRad), 2 μL of primers (5 μM each), 0.16 μL of BSA (Fisher), and 2 μL of DNA extract, with molecular-grade water making up a final volume of 20 μL . qPCRs were run on a CFX96 Connect Real-Time PCR Detection system (BioRad), the thermal cycling protocol included 10 minutes at 95°C, followed by 60 cycles of 30 seconds at 95°C, 30 seconds at 55°C, and 1 minute at 72°C. Samples were tested pure and diluted 10-fold and 100-fold. The 100-fold dilution performed best for all samples and was used for subsequent library preparation. Results indicated higher Fish16S detection per input DNA in the species *Clathrina clathrus* and *Agelas oroides*, which were therefore pinpointed as the best candidates and sequenced individually. The remaining samples were merged per species and sequenced as a pool. All samples were standardized to a concentration of 2.5 ng/ μL to ensure uniform input for amplification. Eight technical replicates per sample were amplified using Fish16S primers tagged with unique 8-base identifiers, to allow sample dereplication during data processing. PCRs were run on a CFX96 Connect Real-Time PCR Detection system (BioRad), the reaction mix consisted of 10 μL of Amplitaq Gold 360 mix (Fisher), 0.16 μL of BSA (Fisher), 2 μL of the primer F&R mix at 5 μM each, 2 μL of DNA extract and molecular grade water for a final volume of 20 μL . The thermal cycling protocol included 10min at 95°C, followed by 48 cycles of 30s at 95°C, 30s at 55°C, 1min at 72°C, and a final elongation step of 7min at 72°C. Samples were purified with the MinElute kit (Qiagen), and products were controlled on a 2% agarose gel (E-Gel Power Snap®, Invitrogen). The library was then constructed and sequenced by FASTERIS (Geneva, Switzerland). It was prepared with the Metafast protocol and sequencing was performed on an Illumina MiSeq platform (2 \times 150 bp).

Bioinformatic analyses

The OBITools suite¹⁹ and SumaClust²⁰ were used for sequence processing and taxonomic assignment. Paired-end reads were merged (illuminapairedend), quality-filtered (obigrep), and dereplicated (obiuniq). Sequences were clustered at 97% similarity (SumaClust), with the most abundant sequence in each cluster retained as the representative cluster center. Clusters containing at least 10 reads in at least one replicate were selected for downstream analysis. Taxonomic assignment was performed with ecotag against a reference database constructed from GenBank entries using *in silico* PCR (ecoPCR) and filtered to retain sequences classified at the family level or higher (obigrep). Further filtering steps using the R package metabar²¹ removed chimeras (best identity <95%), contaminants (contaslayer), low-abundance artefacts (<3% relative frequency, tagjumpslayer), and replicates with sequencing coverage below 100 reads. The remaining PCR replicates were aggregated by sample, and MOTUs observed fewer than 10 times per sample were excluded. The MOTU list was then manually cured

and verified with BLASTn, and MOTUs Fish16S_00009 and Fish16S_00517 assigned only to genus level were renamed as *Diplodus sp1* and *Diplodus sp2*, respectively.

Discussion

We observed marked differences in eDNA recovery across sponge species, with *Axinella verrucosa* outperforming the rest by recovering five of the six detected fish species, thus emerging as the most promising candidate for biomonitoring applications (Figure 2). Notably, it was the only tested species with a standing 3D structure protruding into the water column, a feature that may enhance eDNA capture. With previous studies arguing both in favor⁷ and against¹⁰ a correlation between sponge morphology and eDNA recovery, this aspect warrants further investigation. The *World Porifera Database* lists 100 accepted *Axinella* species, it will be valuable to determine whether others in this genus share similar eDNA retention capabilities. A compelling candidate is *A. polypoides*, an LMA species with a standing 3D structure similar to *A. verrucosa*, though its protected status necessitates careful handling. Our findings also align with previous work showing that LMA sponges recover more eDNA than HMA sponges^{7,12}, reinforcing the need to focus on LMA species in future studies. Including other LMA species such as *Crambe crambe* – not included in this study but known for its antimicrobial compounds^{22,23} and possessing a flat body – will help disentangle the influence of microbial abundance and morphology on eDNA uptake.

The detected fish community was composed of demersal and reef-associated species, highlighting the relevance of sponges as tools for benthic biodiversity monitoring. This is all the most relevant given recent findings suggesting that water eDNA is a poor proxy for benthic biodiversity²⁴, emphasizing the potential of sponges for capturing eDNA from cryptic and substrate-associated taxa. Such ability makes them particularly valuable for monitoring habitats that are difficult to access through conventional methods, such as underwater caves, crevices, and vertical walls. Moreover, while we primarily detected bottom-dwelling species, pelagic fish may be recovered upon further methodological improvements. This is supported by Turon *et al.* (2020)¹⁰ who found no significant detection bias between pelagic and demersal fish when using sponge eDNA.

The overall number of detected fish species was low, and we identify several factors that may have contributed to this outcome. The sampling site lacked structural complexity and no visible fish schools were present during collection, potentially limiting the availability of eDNA in the water column. Additionally, environmental conditions at the time of sampling – such as water temperature – may have influenced DNA persistence and detection. Future campaigns targeting multiple sites and seasons, including high biodiversity MPA's core areas, should overcome this issue. We also identify several methodological improvements that could enhance future studies. These include the immediate transfer of sponges to ethanol upon resurfacing to limit eDNA degradation, the use of multiple genetic markers to overcome reference database incompleteness and increase species detection probability^{18,25}, and improved inhibitor removal during DNA extraction to limit sample inhibition²⁶. Finally, a key priority

Figure 2. Metabarcoding results. Bubble plot depicting the number of Fish16S reads in blue (#Reads) and positive PCR replicates in orange (#pos PCR). Tested sponge species are depicted on the Y-axis with a photography of a representative specimen and their HMA/LMA status (retrieved from refs 11,27. The * mark indicates a predicted status). Detected fish species are indicated on the X-axis with their corresponding habitat (retrieved from FishBase).

is the completion of reference genetic databases. Expanding the current dataset is crucial for accurate species-level assignments, particularly for commercially important taxa such as *Diplodus*, given its importance for fisheries management and conservation.

Overall, *A. verrucosa* stands out as a promising candidate for future eDNA sampling campaigns, yet protocol optimization and further testing of other LMA sponges is warranted. As eDNA-based monitoring advances, sponge sampling offers a valuable complement to water eDNA surveys, especially for benthic communities and habitats where conventional sampling is challenging. Our results arise from a preliminary pilot study for a larger monitoring scheme, yet we share them promptly to benefit MPA practitioners and inform emerging biodiversity monitoring initiatives amid growing national and international demand.

Data availability statement

Zenodo, Evaluation of Mediterranean sponges as natural samplers for environmental DNA (eDNA) - Underlying DATA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14893662>²⁸.

The project contains the following underlying data:

- [Evaluation of Mediterranean sponges as natural samplers for environmental DNA (eDNA) - Underlying DATA.xls'] (comprehensive information on sample treatment and analysis steps, from DNA extraction to metabarcoding analysis).

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC-BY 4.0).

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to the OSU-PYTHEAS diving service, the OMICS platform at MIO, and the Biogeochemistry team leaders, for their support and availability.

References

- Miya M: **Environmental DNA metabarcoding: a novel method for biodiversity monitoring of marine fish communities.** *Ann Rev Mar Sci.* 2022; **14**: 161–185.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Boulanger E, Loiseau N, Valentini A, *et al.*: **Environmental DNA metabarcoding reveals and unpacks a biodiversity conservation paradox in Mediterranean marine reserves.** *Proc Biol Sci.* 2021; **288**(1949): 20210112.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Preston C, Yamahara K, Pargett D, *et al.*: **Autonomous eDNA collection using an uncrewed surface vessel over a 4200-km transect of the Eastern Pacific Ocean.** *Environ DNA.* 2024; **6**(1): e468.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hendricks A, Mackie CM, Luy E, *et al.*: **Compact and automated eDNA sampler for *in situ* monitoring of marine environments.** *Sci Rep.* 2023; **13**(1): 5210.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Mariani S, Baillie C, Colosimo G, *et al.*: **Sponges as natural environmental DNA samplers.** *Curr Biol.* 2019; **29**(11): R401–R402.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Neave EF, Cai W, Arias MB, *et al.*: **Trapped DNA fragments in marine sponge specimens unveil North Atlantic deep-sea fish diversity.** *Proc Biol Sci.* 2023; **290**(2005): 20230771.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Brodnicke OB, Meyer HK, Busch K, *et al.*: **Deep-sea sponge derived environmental DNA analysis reveals demersal fish biodiversity of a remote Arctic ecosystem.** *Environ DNA.* 2023; **5**(6): 1405–1417.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Jeunen GJ, Lamare M, Devine J, *et al.*: **Characterizing Antarctic fish assemblages using eDNA obtained from marine sponge bycatch specimens.** *Rev Fish Biol Fish.* 2024; **34**: 221–238.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Jeunen GJ, Lamare M, Cummings V, *et al.*: **Unveiling the hidden diversity of marine eukaryotes in the Ross Sea: a comparative analysis of seawater and sponge eDNA surveys.** *Environ DNA.* 2023; **5**(6): 1780–1792.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Turon M, Angulo-Preckler C, Antich A, *et al.*: **More than expected from old sponge samples: a natural sampler DNA metabarcoding assessment of marine fish diversity in Nha Trang Bay (Vietnam).** *Front Mar Sci.* 2020; **7**: 605148.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Moitinho-Silva L, Steinert G, Nielsen S, *et al.*: **Predicting the HMA-LMA status in marine sponges by machine learning.** *Front Microbiol.* 2017; **8**: 752.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Cai W, Harper LR, Neave EF, *et al.*: **Environmental DNA persistence and fish detection in captive sponges.** *Mol Ecol Resour.* 2022; **22**(8): 2956–2966.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Bertolino M, Cerrano C, Bavestrello G, *et al.*: **Diversity of Porifera in the Mediterranean coralligenous accretions, with description of a new species.** *ZooKeys.* 2013; (336): 1–37.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- MedPAN and SPA/RAC: **The 2016 status of marine protected areas in the Mediterranean.** By Meola B. and Webster C. Ed SPA/RAC & MedPAN. Tunis 222 pages, 2019.
[Reference Source](#)
- Harper LR, Neave EF, Sellers GS, *et al.*: **Optimized DNA isolation from marine sponges for natural sampler DNA metabarcoding.** *Environ DNA.* 2023; **5**(3): 438–461.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Jeunen GJ, Cane JS, Ferreira S, *et al.*: **Assessing the utility of marine filter feeders for environmental DNA (eDNA) biodiversity monitoring.** *Mol Ecol Resour.* 2023; **23**(4): 771–786.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Shaw JLA, Clarke LJ, Wedderburn SD, *et al.*: **Comparison of environmental DNA metabarcoding and conventional fish survey methods in a river system.** *Biol Conserv.* 2016; **197**: 131–138.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Roblet S, Priouzeau F, Gambini G, *et al.*: **Primer set evaluation and sampling method assessment for the monitoring of fish communities in the North-western part of the Mediterranean Sea through eDNA metabarcoding.** *Environ DNA.* 2024; **6**(3): e554.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Boyer F, Mercier C, Bonin A, *et al.*: **obitools: a unix-inspired software package for DNA metabarcoding.** *Mol Ecol Resour.* 2016; **16**(1): 176–182.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Mercier C, Boyer F, Kopylova E, *et al.*: **SUMATRA and SUMACLUSt: fast and exact comparison and clustering of sequences.** In: *Programs and Abstracts of the SeqBio 2013 Workshop*, 2013; 27–29.
- Zinger L, Lionnet C, Benoiston AS, *et al.*: **metabaR: an R package for the evaluation and improvement of DNA metabarcoding data quality.** *Methods Ecol Evol.* 2021; **12**(4): 586–592.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Jares-Erijman EA, Sakai R, Rinehart KL: **Crambescidins: new antiviral and cytotoxic compounds from the sponge *Crambe crambe*.** *J Org Chem.* 1991; **56**(19): 5712–5715.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Becerro MA, Lopez NI, Turon X, *et al.*: **Antimicrobial activity and surface bacterial film in marine sponges.** *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol.* 1994; **179**(2): 195–205.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Antich A, Palacín C, Cebrian E: **Marine biomonitoring with eDNA: can metabarcoding of water samples cut it as a tool for surveying benthic communities?** *Mol Ecol.* 2021; **30**(13): 3175–3188.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Roblet S, Priouzeau F, Gambini G, *et al.*: **From sight to sequence: Underwater Visual Census vs environmental DNA metabarcoding for the monitoring of taxonomic and functional fish diversity.** *Sci Total Environ.* 2024; **956**: 177250.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Dowell R, Craggs J, Head C, *et al.*: **DNA state influences the uptake and persistence of environmental DNA by marine sponge natural samplers.** 2024.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gloeckner V, Wehr M, Moitinho-Silva L, *et al.*: **The HMA-LMA dichotomy revisited: an electron microscopical survey of 56 sponge species.** *Biol Bull.* 2014; **227**(1): 78–88.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- García Seyda N: **Evaluation of Mediterranean sponges as natural samplers for environmental DNA (eDNA) - underlying DATA.** [Data set]. Zenodo. 2025. <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14893663>

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 1

Reviewer Report 19 May 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21370.r52560>

© 2025 Gallego R. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Ramon Gallego

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

The brief report by Garcia-Seyda and collaborators touches on a timely topic in marine biodiversity surveys - are there some sponge species that are better at capturing environmental DNA than others? And is it a function of their microbiome abundance? The topic is interesting but there are a few methodological choices that make it less useful, and the conclusions dubious.

The authors sample 19 specimens from seven species of sponges from the same environment. One first drawback is that (methods section, first paragraph) "Samples of the same species were stored in Ziploc bags". In my opinion that gets rid of the value of replicates, and now you are left with seven samples.

The authors do their best for keeping extraction protocols standard across samples, although one can only imagine it is hard to standardize 0.5cm³ of tissue.

The authors do a qPCR using fish-specific primers to estimate the amount of fish target DNA inside the sponges. Not mentioned in the main report, but the supplementary material states all samples are in a similar range of fish DNA concentration. The authors then treated the species with bigger numbers (no statistical test for differential concentration of fish DNA) differently to the rest, which they pooled in a single tube per sponge species. I think this is a bad choice.

The sequencing results are not very promising, with only 6 fish species detected in 4 of the 7 sponge pools. This low diversity goes against the results shown in the qPCR assay, and all previous experiments on eDNA retention in sponges, suggesting something must have gone wrong on either the library preparation, the sequencing or the analysis.

It is totally possible that *Axinella* spp. are better eDNA samplers than the other species collected here. However, the results shown are not enough to support or disregard this assumption.

I would encourage them to share the raw sequencing data or at least comment in a results section how did the sequencing perform.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

No

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: eDNA, metabarcoding, bioinformatics, nsDNA

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 23 Sep 2025

Nicolas Garcia Seyda

We sincerely thank the reviewer for the time and effort dedicated to evaluating our manuscript, as well as for the constructive feedback provided. Below, we address each comment in a point-by-point manner:

COMMENT 1: The authors sample 19 specimens from seven species of sponges from the same environment. One first drawback is that (methods section, first paragraph) "Samples of the same species were stored in Ziploc bags". In my opinion that gets rid of the value of replicates, and now you are left with seven samples.

RESPONSE 1: As now clarified in the main text, sample pooling is a common strategy in screening studies to reduce experimental costs and workload. Given the absence of prior knowledge on which species might perform better—and the possibility that some species might yield no detectable result (as occurred with three of the seven tested species)—biological replicates are initially pooled to generate a single sample per species. Once promising candidates are identified, a follow-up campaign with independent replicates is conducted to validate the initial findings. In recognition of the preliminary nature of these results, we have now added a "Limitations of the Study" section to explicitly highlight the constraints and drawbacks of this approach.

COMMENT 2: The authors do their best for keeping extraction protocols standard across samples, although one can only imagine it is hard to standardize 0.5cm³ of tissue.

RESPONSE 2: The 0.5cm³ of tissue has been recurrently used in the literature (see Jeunen 2023, Cai 2022). In addition, DNA input was normalized following the extraction.

COMMENT 3: The authors do a qPCR using fish-specific primers to estimate the amount of fish target DNA inside the sponges. Not mentioned in the main report, but the supplementary material states all samples are in a similar range of fish DNA concentration. The authors then treated the species with bigger numbers (no statistical test for differential concentration of fish DNA) differently to the rest, which they pooled in a single tube per sponge species. I think this is a bad choice. The sequencing results are not very promising, with only 6 fish species detected in 4 of the 7 sponge pools. This low diversity goes against the results shown in the qPCR assay, and all previous experiments on eDNA retention in sponges, suggesting something must have gone wrong on either the library preparation, the sequencing or the analysis.

RESPONSE 3: The inconsistencies between qPCR and sequencing results have now been clarified in the revised manuscript. Specifically, the underlying dataset, Methods, and Discussion have been updated to explain that the Fish16S primers likely produced artifactual amplifications. This is evidenced by the numerous MOTUs with a low best identity value (<0.65) in Table 6 (Underlying data), and may explain why *Chondrosia clathrus* and *Aplysina oroides* showed high apparent fish eDNA concentrations by qPCR, but yielded very few validated reads after bioinformatic filtering.

Regarding sequencing performance, the results are in fact consistent with previous reports for Mediterranean sponges. Mariani et al. (2019) detected four and seven fish taxa from *Ircinia fasciculata* and *Petrosia ficiformis*, respectively, from two different sites and using 12S (Teleo02) primers. Corral-Lou et al. (2025) reported six fish taxa (four at species level) from 32 *Haliclona cinerea* and *Haliclona mediterranea* specimens sampled across four sites and two seasons with COI primers (mlCOIintF-XT / jgHCO2198). By comparison, our study based on 19 specimens collected at a single site during a single season recovered a comparable number of taxa.

COMMENT 4: It is totally possible that *Axinella* spp. are better eDNA samplers than the other species collected here. However, the results shown are not enough to support or disregard this assumption.

I would encourage them to share the raw sequencing data or at least comment in a results section how did the sequencing perform.

RESPONSE 4: The underlying dataset has been revised to include previously missing information, and the raw sequencing data has also been uploaded. In addition, the manuscript has been revised to adopt more cautious interpretations. Specifically, we have downgraded general claims regarding sponge performance and added a "Limitations of the Study" section to explicitly acknowledge the absence of statistical analyses, due to the screening nature of this study.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 18 April 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21370.r52562>

© 2025 Ruiz-Ramos D. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Dannise V. Ruiz-Ramos

University of Maryland Eastern Shore, Princess Anne, MD, USA

In this brief report, Garcia-Seyda et al. evaluate the usefulness of marine sponges as natural eDNA samplers for the Mediterranean Sea. They test seven sponge species based on their availability and microbial abundance (HMA vs. LMA). They conclude that *Axinella verrucosa* might be the best sponge to use as a natural eDNA sampler. It is unclear whether *A. verrucosa* is a common species, as only two individuals were found at the site. This is an interesting pilot study, but the limited data and low detections make recommending a specific species as a natural sampler challenging. From the limited data presented, I'm not sure if sponges would be a better alternative to water samples, but they could serve as an alternative for rapid monitoring during an emergency.

Specific comments: (There are no lines in the manuscript, so I tried to give approximate locations.)

Last paragraph of methods: "Results indicated higher Fish16S detection per input DNA in the species *Clathrina clathrus* and *Agelas oroides*, which were therefore pinpointed as the best candidates and sequenced individually. The remaining samples were merged per species and sequenced as a pool." There is no discussion on how this decision affected the results in Fig 2 and your conclusion. Were *A. verrucosa* samples pooled, while others were not? That could affect the diversity of MOTUs. This lack of information makes Figure 2 misleading.

Methods: change "products were controlled on a 2% agarose gel" to "products were verified"

Discussion:

If *Clathrina clathrus* and *Agelas oroides* were the samples with higher 16S detections, why are there no results in Fig 2? I think this lack of sequencing results should be discussed. Why did you decide *A. verrucosa* performed better? There is no statistical test.

Change: "Axinella verrucosa outperforming the rest by recovering five of the six detected fish species, thus emerging as the most promising candidate for biomonitoring applications" Change to 4 species?

How many species from the genus *Diplodus* are found in the study area? If MOTU was only assigned to the genus level, it could be a degraded sequence of *D. sargus*. So, based on the MOTU information (no percent identity given), you have four species, not 6.

Maybe as natural samplers the 3D structure of the sponge is more important than the species?

Delete point in "standing 3D structure similar to *A. verrucosa*."

Second paragraph: change "community" for species.

"The detected fish community was composed of demersal and reef-associated species, highlighting the relevance of sponges as tools for benthic biodiversity monitoring. This is all the most relevant given recent findings suggesting that water eDNA is a poor proxy for benthic biodiversity, emphasizing the potential of sponges for capturing eDNA from cryptic and substrate-associated taxa." Maybe the authors have data from other markers to sustain these claims, but based on the results here, sponges are also poor indicators of benthic biodiversity (only 2 benthic fish species were detected).

"Overall, *A. verrucosa* stands out as a promising candidate for future eDNA sampling campaigns, yet protocol optimization and further testing of other LMA sponges is warranted." I do not think the presented data supports this claim.

Peer review form:

- Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature? Yes
- Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit? Yes, for a brief report. However, it is suggested that authors present the full data or adjust their conclusions.
- Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others? Methods are well detailed, analysis is deficient.
- If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate? Data is limited, but I understand it is a brief report. Please report the results of the negative PCR control. Were only two replicates run for the negative control? From Figure 2, samples were run in triplicate, but the qPCR full data in supplementary materials shows only one sample, and two PCR negative control. Check the MIQE guidelines for reporting qPCR data. Also, there are no statistical analyses to test whether high-microbial-activity sponges were different from low-microbial-activity sponges. The authors should be more cautious with their interpretation since only three samples had two or more positive PCR replicates, and one of those samples was a high-microbial-activity sponge. Based on Figure 2, *A. verrucosa* only recovered two more fish species than the other species.
- Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility? No, the data is incomplete. The data from sample extraction to qPCR results is available. Supplemental data is unclear, authors need to include definition of columns and the metadata for the data to be useful. The metabarcoding sequence table and link to the sequence depository are missing (only the sequence count is available).
- Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results? No. It is not clear if all the samples were sequenced; the sampling pooling tab suggests 16 samples were sequenced (MIOA001-04, MIOA007, MIOA010-14, MIOA16, MIO19), the table "MOTUs dataset per sample" shows a summary of counts for samples MIOA002, MIOA013, MIOA014, and MIOA019. Where are the rest of the samples? If they were not sequenced, please say so. It renders Fig2 misleading. Did the authors amplify and sequence *A. cavernicola*, *P. piriformis*, and *C. reniformis* and did not recover any sequence? If those samples were not amplified and sequenced, please remove them from Fig 2.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Marine biology, environmental DNA, environmental omics.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 23 Sep 2025

Nicolas Garcia Seyda

We sincerely thank the reviewer for the time and effort dedicated to evaluating our manuscript, as well as for the constructive feedback provided. Below, we address each comment in a point-by-point manner:

COMMENT 1: "Results indicated higher Fish16S detection per input DNA in the species *Clathrina clathrus* and *Agelas oroides*, which were therefore pinpointed as the best candidates and sequenced individually. The remaining samples were merged per species and sequenced as a pool." There is no discussion on how this decision affected the results in Fig 2 and your conclusion. Were *A. verrucosa* samples pooled, while others were not? That could affect the diversity of MOTUs. This lack of information makes Figure 2 misleading.

RESPONSE 1: The main text and figure legend have been updated to clarify that all biological replicates were pooled, leading to 1 sequenced sample per sponge species, except for *Clathrina clathrus* and *Agelas oroides* which were sequenced individually but retrieved few sequences after bioinformatic analysis.

COMMENT 2: change "products were controlled on a 2% agarose gel" to "products were

verified”

RESPONSE 2: The text has been changed accordingly.

COMMENT 3: If *Clathrina clathrus* and *Agelas oroides* were the samples with higher 16S detections, why are there no results in Fig 2? I think this lack of sequencing results should be discussed. Why did you decide *A. verrucosa* performed better? There is no statistical test.

RESPONSE 3: The discrepancy between qPCR results and retrieved sequences has been added to the main text and the underlying data. The figure and its legend have been updated to clarify the sample-pooling strategy.

COMMENT 4: “*Axinella verrucosa* outperforming the rest by recovering five of the six detected fish species, thus emerging as the most promising candidate for biomonitoring applications” Change to 4 species?

RESPONSE 4: We have updated to 5 taxa, as indeed some detections (*Diplodus*) did not arrive at species level. The general claim has also been downgraded to remain cautious about our conclusions.

COMMENT 5: How many species from the genus *Diplodus* are found in the study area? If MOTU was only assigned to the genus level, it could be a degraded sequence of *D. sargus*. So, based on the MOTU information (no percent identity given), you have four species, not 6.

RESPONSE 5: Several *Diplodus* species are found in the study area, including *Diplodus vulgaris*, *Diplodus sargus*, *Diplodus cervinus* and *Diplodus puntazzo*. Comprehensive MOTU data, including percent identity, have been added to the underlying dataset. MOTU “Fish16S_00009” (renamed *Diplodus* sp. 1) shows 98.5% similarity to *D. vulgaris* based on a manual BLAST search of GenBank records. However, the three *Diplodus* sequences retrieved are also 98.5% similar to each other, which appears to represent the average level of similarity within the genus. As a result, they cannot be confidently assigned to a particular species and were therefore reported at the highest reliable taxonomic resolution, namely the genus level (i.e., *Diplodus* sp.1, *Diplodus* sp.2).

COMMENT 6: Maybe as natural samplers the 3D structure of the sponge is more important than the species?

RESPONSE 6: Indeed, the impact of 3D structure on eDNA recovery is mentioned in the discussion. However, a quantitative morphometric analysis of the sampled specimens would be required to rigorously assess the relationship between structural complexity and eDNA yield.

COMMENT 7: Delete point in” standing 3D structure similar to *A. verrucosa*.,”

RESPONSE 7: The text has been changed accordingly.

COMMENT 8: Second paragraph: change “community” for species.

RESPONSE 8: The text has been changed accordingly.

COMMENT 9: “The detected fish community was composed of demersal and reef-associated species, highlighting the relevance of sponges as tools for benthic biodiversity monitoring. This is all the most relevant given recent findings suggesting that water eDNA is a poor proxy for benthic biodiversity, emphasizing the potential of sponges for capturing eDNA from cryptic and substrate-associated taxa.” Maybe the authors have data from other markers to sustain these claims, but based on the results here, sponges are also poor indicators of benthic biodiversity (only 2 benthic fish species were detected).

RESPONSE 9: The text has been clarified to state that sponges may be good indicators of substrate-associated or bottom-dwelling taxa, ie. species living in close proximity to the seabed. For fish, following Fishbase habitat-descriptors, this would refer to benthic, demersal and reef-associated species, in opposition to those thriving in the water column (strictly pelagic species).

COMMENT 10: “Overall, *A. verrucosa* stands out as a promising candidate for future eDNA sampling campaigns, yet protocol optimization and further testing of other LMA sponges is warranted.” I do not think the presented data supports this claim.

RESPONSE 10: The conclusion has been revised to adopt a more cautious interpretation: “*A. verrucosa* appears to recover more fish eDNA, making it a promising candidate for further protocol refinement.” Additionally, we have added a “Limitations of the Study” section to explicitly acknowledge the limitations of our work, including the inability to perform statistical analyses and, consequently, to definitively determine whether *A. verrucosa* or other LMA sponges are superior candidates for eDNA sampling.

COMMENT 11: Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit? Yes, for a brief report. However, it is suggested that authors present the full data or adjust their conclusions.

RESPONSE 11: Claims have been downgraded and data completed to address the reviewer’s concerns

COMMENT 12: Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others? Methods are well detailed, analysis is deficient.

RESPONSE 12: Because of the screening nature of the project, and the subsequent pooling of samples, statistical analysis is not possible. This notion has been added to the main text.

COMMENT 13: If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate? Data is limited, but I understand it is a brief report. Please report the results of the negative PCR control. Were only two replicates run for the negative control? From Figure 2, samples were run in triplicate, but the qPCR full data in supplementary materials shows only one sample, and two PCR negative control. Check the MIQE guidelines for reporting qPCR data.

Also, there are no statistical analyses to test whether high-microbial-activity sponges were different from low-microbial-activity sponges. The authors should be more cautious with their interpretation since only three samples had two or more positive PCR replicates, and one of those samples was a high-microbial-activity sponge. Based on Figure 2, *A. verrucosa* only recovered two more fish species than the other species.

RESPONSE 13: The legend of the figure has been updated to clarify the use of a total of eight PCR replicates, as described in the Methods. The underlying dataset has also been revised to include previously missing information, including the results of positive and negative PCR controls. Finally, the manuscript has been revised to adopt more cautious interpretations. Specifically, we have downgraded general claims regarding sponge performance and added a "Limitations of the Study" section to explicitly acknowledge the absence of statistical analyses, due to the screening nature of this study.

COMMENT 14: Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility? No, the data is incomplete. The data from sample extraction to qPCR results is available. Supplemental data is unclear, authors need to include definition of columns and the metadata for the data to be useful. The metabarcoding sequence table and link to the sequence depository are missing (only the sequence count is available).

RESPONSE 14: The underlying data file has been revised to incorporate the corrections and address the reviewer's concerns.

COMMENT 15: Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results? No. It is not clear if all the samples were sequenced; the sampling pooling tab suggests 16 samples were sequenced (MIOA001-04, MIOA007, MIOA010-14, MIOA16, MIO19), the table "MOTUs dataset per sample" shows a summary of counts for samples MIOA002, MIOA013, MIOA014, and MIOA019. Where are the rest of the samples? If they were not sequenced, please say so. It renders Fig2 misleading. Did the authors amplify and sequence *A. cavernicola*, *P. piriformis*, and *C. reniformis* and did not recover any sequence? If those samples were not amplified and sequenced, please remove them from Fig 2.

RESPONSE 15: All samples were sequenced, yet some did not retrieve any sequence after the bioinformatic cleaning steps. This has been now clarified in the methods and Fig 2 legend.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.